

CP11: MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591

CP19: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871

CP23: MtrunA17_Ch1g0200071

CP34: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461

+2 (2a→1r)

CP45: MtrunA17_Chr2g0328091

CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761

-2 (2r→3a)

+2 (1a2→3a1)

+1 (1r→2a)

-2 (3a1→1a2)

Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 5. A graphical summary on folding predictions for 24 MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) that contain beta-sheets regardless of the presence of alpha-helices. For each CP, one image is displayed: the predicted folding structure (top) along with heat maps of five predictions (bottom). The rest of the legend is the same as for Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 1.